

RESISTANT STARCH: A HOPE FOR BETTER HUMAN HEALTH

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Dietary adjustments might prevent or mitigate many chronic health issues in both developing and wealthy countries. White bread, cakes, and noodles are examples of typical starchy meals that have a high percentage of highly digestible starch. Because there is worry that such fast digested starches may contribute to chronic illness in humans and animals, starches that are resistant to digestive enzymes have become the subject of increased scientific attention. Such starches, known as resistant starches, have been intensively studied in terms of their health characteristics, increasing their presence in food components, health and functional features as a dietary element, and involvement in gut health, presumably through butyrate generation. Resistant starch is starch that cannot be digested by amylases in the small intestine and instead

travels to the colon to be fermented by bacteria. Englyst coined the phrase “resistant starch” for the first time in the 1980s (Englyst et al., 1982). Americans consume just about 5 g of resistant starch on average each day, far less than the minimum 6 g per meal that is advised for health advantages.

Advantages of Resistant Starch

Starches are normally broken down into glucose when digested. Resistant starch does not elevate glucose because it is not digested in the small intestine. Gut health improves when fermentation in the large intestine produces more healthy bacteria and fewer harmful bacteria. Glycemic management can be improved by having healthy gut flora. Other advantages of resistant starch include enhanced fullness, constipation treatment and prevention, decreased cholesterol, and a lower risk of colon cancer. Because resistant starch ferments slowly, it produces less gas than other fibres. Other benefits are included as-

Types of resistant Starch

There are now five forms of resistant starch-

Types	Description	Example
RS1	Starch that is physically unavailable	Grain, coarsely milled or whole-kernel
RS2	B- or C-polymorphed granular starch	Maize starch with high amylose, raw potato starch, and raw banana starch
RS3	Retrograded starch	Starchy meals that have been cooked and cooled
RS4	Chemically altered starches	Octenyl succinate starch with cross-linked starch
RS5	Amylose-lipid mixture	High-amylose starch complexed with stearic acid

Diabetes control and prevention-

Diabetes is a condition that affects blood sugar levels. When you have diabetes, your body has difficulty processing carbs. This can result in dangerously low blood sugar (hypoglycemia) or dangerously high blood sugar crises (hyperglycemia). Diabetes can lead to heart disease, renal disease, stroke, and other major health problems over time. Simple carbs quickly elevate blood sugar levels, which can be dangerous for diabetics. Because complex carbohydrate rich diets with resistant starches take a long time to digest, they maintain constant blood sugar levels. This helps to avert diabetic crises in the short run.

Cancer prevention-

Consuming a diet rich in resistant starches can help prevent many cancers. This includes cancer of the breast, the colon, and other digestive system organs.

Weight control-

Consuming resistant starches keeps you satisfied for longer. This can help you avoid overeating. The beneficial effect of resistant starches on blood sugar stability can also help to avoid weight gain.

Stool Assistance-

Resistant starches can aid in stool loosening and constipation relief. Constipation may be avoided by reducing constipation. Diarrhea can also be avoided by using resistant starches.

Foods Sources

Foods that contain resistant starch include:

- Green plantains with bananas (as a banana ripens the starch changes to a regular starch)
- Lentils, peas, and beans (white beans and lentils are the highest in resistant starch)
- Oats and barley are examples of whole grains.
- Rice, cooked and cooled
- Heat changes the quantity of resistant starch. When oats, green bananas, and plantains are cooked, they lose part of their resistant starch. During the cooking and chilling process, another sort of resistant starch is formed. Cooked rice that has been cooled has more resistant starch than uncooked rice.

How to Incorporate Resistant Starch into Diet

- Cook rice, potatoes, beans, and pasta a day ahead of time and store in the refrigerator overnight. It is acceptable to reheat the starch

before serving. Reheating has no effect on the quantity of resistant starch.

- In place of cooked oatmeal, soak uncooked oats overnight in yoghurt, milk, or a nondairy milk (often called overnight oats).
- Lentils can be added to salads or soups.
- Try green banana flour, plantain flour, cassava flour, or potato starch as a partial flour alternative. When baking or cooking with these flours, resistant starch is lost. You may also add a tiny quantity (1-2 tablespoons) to your diet to complement.

To avoid GI adverse effects, increase fibre intake gradually and drink lots of water. Remember that all fibre has health advantages, so consume a variety of fiber-rich foods.

References-

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